

Productivity and Research Competencies Required by Business Educators for Teaching Digital Marketing Courses in Universities in South South Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was carried out to determine productivity and research competencies required by business educators for teaching digital marketing courses in universities in South-south Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Two research purposes, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study was 207 business educators in the department of vocational and technology education (business education option). A 20-item questionnaire, structured on a 4-point response of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE) was used in collecting data for the study. The data collected were analyzed using weighted mean score while t-test statistics were used for testing the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The study identified two major competencies required by business educators for teaching digital marketing courses in south-south Nigeria which are; productivity competency and research competency. There was no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which productivity and research competencies are required for teaching digital marketing in South-south Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends, among others, that University administration, in conjunction with experienced project managers, should develop and oversee the implementation of a project-management training program tailored to digital marketing projects.

Keywords: Marketing, Productivity, Research, Competencies, Teaching, Digital Marketing

Introduction

Marketing, an ancient discipline combining science and art, remains fluid and ever-changing. In today's world, marketing permeates virtually every facet of our lives, influencing the majority of tasks we undertake. Its influence extends across our daily routines and encompasses all aspects of business endeavors. Kotler, Kartjaya and Setiawan (2018) assert that marketing isn't merely one function within a business but rather represents the entire business when viewed from the customer's perspective. With technological advancements and its critical role in business, marketing has transformed into a more intricate and captivating state. Given its pivotal role in human activities, marketing adapts to every technological shift, originating from the days of barter trade, progressing through traditional marketing, and evolving into the digital marketing landscape we witness today. The emergence of this fresh approach has placed significant demands on various sectors, including educators in universities who teach marketing courses. They are now required

to possess essential digital marketing competencies to effectively convey the necessary knowledge and employability skills to their students' pursuing degrees in marketing within the realm of business education.

Before the advent of digital marketing in the 1990s and up until the late twentieth century, marketing concepts were taught in Nigerian universities using traditional methods. Business educators were trained to align with curriculum designs focused on imparting traditional marketing principles and practices to graduates. The shift from traditional to digital marketing has been so profound that many of these educators, who were well-versed in traditional marketing, have encountered challenges in acquiring the necessary digital marketing skills.

While some educators have made personal efforts to adapt by acquiring ICT devices such as laptops and projectors or even enrolling in private institutions to gain digital marketing expertise, the question remains whether educators in government universities can effectively teach digital marketing and impart essential digital marketing knowledge and skills to marketing education graduates. It is disheartening to note that marketing education graduates continue to struggle to secure employment, with some resorting to illegal activities like commercial sex work, oil bunkering, internet fraud, kidnapping, and more. This starkly contradicts the fundamental objective of vocational education, which aims to equip graduates with employability skills and self-sufficiency. This situation may also explain why graduates trained in traditional marketing within our universities may not be suitable for sectors where digital marketing principles and practices are essential.

Given these circumstances, one can infer that the competencies acquired by business educators for teaching traditional marketing may have become obsolete and irrelevant when it comes to instructing digital marketing courses in our universities. Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) identified six critical digital marketing and ICT competencies, including communication, productivity, presentation, media, research, and problem-solving competencies.

Objectives of the Study

The following two objectives guided the study:

1. Marketing productivity competency is required by business educators for teaching digital marketing in state and federal universities in South-South Nigeria.
2. Marketing research competency is required by business educators for teaching digital marketing in state and federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was directed by the following research questions:

1. To what extent is marketing productivity a competency required by business educators for teaching digital marketing in state and federal universities in South-South Nigeria?
2. To what extent is marketing research a competency required by business educators for teaching digital marketing in state and federal universities in South-South Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which marketing productivity is a competency required for teaching digital marketing in South-South Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which marketing research is a competency required for teaching digital marketing in South-South Nigeria.

Productivity and Research Competencies

Productivity competencies encompass tasks such as creating documents, retrieving information, manipulating text, printing, managing files, being familiar with word processing programs like MS Word and Word Perfect, possessing elementary knowledge in computer hardware, understanding operating systems, knowing computer startup and shutdown procedures, and being proficient in using a mouse/ keyboard. Adoption of information and communication technology possesses optimistic effect on output development, especially in companies that heavily rely on information and communication technology. However, the distinction in information and communication technology adoption including its productive impact across countries remains puzzling. ICT competency, essentially, involves the effective use of computers for productivity (Ahmed 2016).

Research competency involves the effective utilization of online search strategies, the assessment of online information and sources, as well as the saving and citation of online information and sources (Okoye&Ugwuogo2021). The authors link research competence in utilization of ICT for research purposes. In the realm of academia, research essentially entails to develop, generate, discover, invent, and create innovative ideas. In institutions, research serves as a crucial instrument for academic accomplishment and the pursuit of excellence. Furthermore, research employs a vital function in assessing the growth of competent professionals, serving as one of the standards for accreditation. Additionally, when evaluating programs and institutions for accreditation, the research component becomes a significant focal point. This underscores a university's capacity to produce research that contributes to the productivity of the institution.

Methods

The study adopted the descriptive survey. The researcher's choice to adopt this design aligns with the research work, as it involves gathering opinions and factual information from a sample representing the broader population of business educators regarding the competencies necessary for teaching digital marketing. According to Ukachi (2017), a descriptive survey research design entails investigating a subset of a population with the aim of describing, explaining, and documenting the current state or absence of a phenomenon under examination. Similarly, Offor (2022) defined descriptive survey research as the process of describing specific characteristics or attributes of a population based on data collected from a representative sample within that population. The population of the study comprised all business educators in the faculties of education offering business education (marketing education option) at both state and federal universities located in the South-South region of Nigeria. At the time this research was conducted,

there were a total of 207 business educators spread across the eleven selected universities offering Business Education. Consequently, the entire population for this study will encompass these 207 business educators.

Due to the reasonably small size of the population, the total population size of 207 was used for the study, making it unnecessary to employ any sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection for this study was a researcher-designed structured questionnaire named "Media and Presentation Competencies of Business Educators for Teaching Digital Marketing Questionnaire (MPCBETDMQ)." The questionnaire is divided into two sections, labelled as Section A and Section B. Section A centre on respondents' demographic information, including the type of university (state or federal), institutional location, department, faculty, and area of specialization. Section B encompasses twenty (20) item statements designed to solicit opinions from the respondents regarding the subject matter. These items were categorized into two (2) clusters aligned with the research questions. The clusters were as follows: productivity competency for teaching digital marketing (ten items) and research competency. The response options for the respondents were "Very High Extent (VHE); High Extent (HE); Low Extent (LE); and "Very Low Extent (VLE) and rated 4, 3, 2 and 1 on a 4-point Likert scale. The research instrument was validated by three experts from the Measurement and Evaluation unit, Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University. These validators were provided with copies of the instrument to assess and validate the items for the study. They offered relevant suggestions and corrections, which were subsequently integrated into the final version of the questionnaire. To evaluate the instrument's internal consistency, the Cronbach's Alpha co-efficient reliability test was utilized.

The instrument was administered once to twenty (20) business educators from public universities in South-East Nigeria, specifically NnamdiAzikiwe University, Anambra State (eight respondents), and Imo State University, Owerri (twelve respondents). The obtained reliability co-efficient values were 0.80, 0.83, 0.79, 0.80, 0.82, and 0.79 for media, presentation, productivity, research, problem-solving, and communication competencies, respectively. The grand mean reliability value was 0.84. The various reliability values and the grand mean reliability value were within the Cronbach Reliability coefficient threshold of 0.7- 0.99, (Nunnally, 1978), thus showing a high reliability of the instrument for data collection. The research questions, mean and standard deviation calculations were used. Mean scores response equal to or greater than 2.50 criterion score was considered as an indication of high extent, whereas a mean response score below 2.50 indicated low extent. In relation to hypothesis testing, the probability value (p-value) was employed. If the p-value is less than or equal to the 0.05 alpha level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. Conversely, if the p-value exceeds the 0.05 alpha level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_0) was accepted.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent is marketing productivity a competency required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria?

Table 1

Mean and standard deviation on the extent to which productivity competency is required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities.

Item statement	Federal University		State University		Total		Remark
	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	
1. Creating a document of various types on marketing courses and save in a desired location on your system.	3.00	0.84	3.28	0.87	3.19	0.87	High extent
2.	3.23	0.92	3.42		3.36	0.83	High extent

	Name, rename, copy and delete file with ease.				0.79			
3.	Ability to check for and install operating system update.	3.27	0.97	3.20	0.86	3.22	0.90	High extent
4.	Create and manipulate programs using both Microsoft Word and WordPerfect.	3.13	0.86	2.89	0.95	2.96	0.93	High extent
5.	Ability to verify the available storage space on a drive and storage device within electronic devices.	3.08	0.79	3.31	0.84	3.24	0.83	High extent
6.	Ability to understand the basic functions and usage of a window, or Macintosh Operating System.	2.85	0.92	3.08	0.86	3.01	0.88	High extent
7.	Capability to comprehend and oversee the organization of files on a computer and various electronic devices.	3.19	0.84	3.27	0.62	3.25	0.70	High extent
8.	Using a mouse pointing device and keyboard optimally.	2.67	0.88	3.23	0.87	3.06	0.91	High extent
9.	Capability to employ assistance and technical expertise for resolving common issues.	3.04	0.89	3.04	0.96	3.04	0.93	High extent
10.	Download and install soft wares in a disk.	3.10	1.03	3.03	0.95	3.05	0.98	High extent
	Grand mean	3.06	0.89	3.16	0.86	3.14	0.88	High extent

Key: $\bar{X}$ = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; Criterion Score = 2.50, Population = 52 respondents for federal universities; 118 respondents for state universities. **Source:** Researcher's Field work (2024)

Table 1 presented the mean range scores and standard deviation, reflecting the extent to which marketing productivity is a competency required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in both federal and state universities located in South-South Nigeria. The results for the items range from 3.00 to 3.10 with their corresponding standard deviations of 0.84 to 1.03 for federal universities. The results for state universities range from 3.28 to 3.42, with corresponding standard deviations results of 0.87 to 0.95. Specifically, it showcases the collective mean scores for items 21 through 30, which range from 3.19 to 3.05, along with their corresponding standard deviations of 0.87 to 0.98.

Since the mean response scores for all the 10 items for both federal and state universities were above the criterion response score of 2.50, it means, that marketing productivity was a competency required by business educators in the teaching of digital marketing. This indicates that Business Educators in both federal and state universities place a significant emphasis on acquiring

competencies related to tasks such as creating various types of documents in marketing courses and saving them in preferred locations on their computer systems. They are expected to possess skills like naming, renaming, copying, and deleting files with ease, checking for and installing operating system updates, as well as developing and processing programs like MS Word and Word Perfect. Additionally, Business Educators should be proficient in checking the available storage space on electronic devices, understanding the fundamental functions and usage of both Windows and Macintosh Operating Systems, managing the file structure of computers and other electronic devices, optimizing the use of mouse pointing devices and keyboards, utilizing help resources, troubleshooting routine problems, and downloading and installing software from a disk.

Furthermore, the grand mean rating score of federal universities business educators (3.06) was less than that of the state universities business educators (3.16) with a total grand rating mean score of (3.14) being greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This simply means that, state universities business educators mean rating score was better than that of the federal universities business educators on their rating of the extent marketing productivity competency is required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria. Consequent upon the observed difference the mean rating scores were further subjected to t-test analysis in order to ascertain if the difference observed is significant or not.

Research Question Two

To what extent is marketing research competency required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria?

Table 2

Mean and standard deviation on the extent to which marketing research competency is required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities.

	Item statement	Federal University		State University		Total		Remark
		$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	
11	Ability to carry out effective online marketing research.	2.98	0.85	3.30	0.73	3.20	0.78	High extent
12	Ability to analyse/interpret internet marketing information/data.	2.98	0.70	2.96	0.79	2.96	0.76	High extent
13	Ability to acquire new knowledge and ideas using online materials.	2.67	1.06	3.43	0.63	3.20	0.86	High extent
		3.12	0.83	3.23	0.74	3.19	0.77	High extent

14	Ability to find out what companies do to increase their sales online							
15	Collecting data and analyse them to know which social network or electronic device promotes internet sales better.	2.81	0.86	3.08	0.85	3.00	0.86	High extent
16	Involvement with private/government marketing firms on internet marketing.	2.81	0.72	2.81	0.90	2.81	0.84	High extent
17	Supervision of students' projects on digital marketing.	2.77	0.92	2.92	1.03	2.87	1.00	High extent
18	Ability to carry out online marketing research to determine what customers or client's needs.	2.54	0.90	2.99	0.73	2.85	0.81	High extent
19	Building a mouse trap to create website fit within your overall digital marketing activities.	2.81	0.74	2.72	0.96	2.75	0.90	High extent
20	Ability to develop digital marketing research questionnaires	2.90	0.80	3.27	0.76	3.16	0.79	High extent
	Grand mean	2.84	0.84	3.07	0.81	2.99	0.84	

Key: $\bar{X}$ = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; Criterion Score = 2.50, Population = 52 respondents for federal universities; 118 respondents for state universities. **Source:** Researcher's Field work (2024)

Table 2 presented the mean range scores and standard deviation, reflecting the extent to which marketing research is a competency required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in both federal and state universities located in South-South Nigeria. The results from item 11-20 range from 2.98 to 2.90 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.85 to 0.80 for federal universities. The results for state universities range from 3.20 to 3.16 with corresponding standard deviations results of 0.78 to 0.79. Since the mean response scores for all the 10 items for both federal and state universities were above the criterion response score of 2.50, it means, that marketing research was a competency required by business educators in the teaching of digital marketing.

This signifies that Business Educators in both federal and state universities place substantial importance on acquiring competencies related to various aspects of marketing research in the digital realm. These competencies encompass the ability to conduct effective online marketing research, analyse and interpret internet marketing information and data, acquire new knowledge and ideas using online resources, investigate strategies employed by companies to enhance their online sales, collect and analyse data to identify the most effective social networks and electronic devices for promoting internet sales, collaborate with private and government marketing firms for

internet marketing initiatives, supervise students' projects in the field of digital marketing, conduct online marketing research to understand customers' needs, create websites tailored to digital marketing activities, and formulate digital marketing research questionnaires.

Furthermore, the grand mean rating score of federal universities business educators (2.84) was less than that of the state universities business educators (3.07) with a total grand rating mean score of (2.99) being greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This simply means that, state universities business educators mean rating score was better than that of the federal universities business educators on their rating of the extent marketing research competency is required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria. Consequent upon the observed difference the mean rating scores were further subjected to t-test analysis in order to ascertain if the difference observed is significant or not.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of the responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which marketing productivity as a competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South-South Nigeria.

Table 3

Independent t-test analysis of the difference in mean responses of state and federal universities business educators on marketing productivity competency is required for teaching digital marketing

University	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	P-value or sig	Alpha level	Decision
Federal	52	30.56	5.94	168	-1.297	0.196.	0.05	Not sig
State	118	31.76	5.42					p>0.05

Key: $\bar{X}$ = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; df =168; t = -1.297; P-value = 0.196; Alph level 0.05 Source: Researcher's Field work (2024)

Table 3 indicates the independent t-test analysis of the difference in mean responses of state and federal universities business educators on marketing productivity competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South-south Nigeria. Federal universities business educators have a mean of 30.56 with a standard deviation of 5.94 while state universities business educators have a mean of 31.76 with a standard deviation of 5.42. It can be discerned from the table that, the observed probability value (p-value) or sig at 0.05 level of significance with 168 degrees of freedom is .196, which is greater than the alpha level, $t(168) = -1.297, p>0.05$. Since the p-value is greater than the alpha level, the null hypothesis of "There is no significant difference between the mean responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which

marketing productivity competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South-south Nigeria” is accepted.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of the responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which marketing research as a competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South-South Nigeria.

Table 4

Independent t-test analysis of the difference in mean responses of state and federal universities business educators on marketing research competency is required for teaching digital marketing

University	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	P-value or sig	Alpha level	Decision
Federal	52	28.38	5.09	168	-2.778	0.006.	0.05	Sig
State	118	30.71	5.01					P<0.05

Key: $\bar{X}$ = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; df =168; t = -2.778; P-value = 0.006; Alpha level 0.05 **Source:** Researcher’s Field work (2024)

Table 4 indicates the independent t-test analysis of the difference in mean responses of state and federal universities business educators on marketing research competencies required for teaching digital marketing in South-south Nigeria. Federal universities business educators have a mean of 28.38 with a standard deviation of 5.09 while state universities business educators have a mean of 31.71 with a standard deviation of 5.01. It can be discerned from the table that, the observed probability value (p-value) or sig at 0.05 level of significance with 168 degrees of freedom is .006, which is less than the alpha level, $t(168) = -2.778, p < 0.05$. Since the p-value is less than the alpha level, the null hypothesis of “There is no significant difference between the mean responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which marketing research competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South South Nigeria” is rejected, therefore the alternative hypothesis is upheld. This implies that, there is a significant difference between the mean responses of business educators in state and federal universities on the extent to which marketing research competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South-south Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation on the extent to which productivity competency is required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria. The total mean of items were above the criterion mean of 2.50 which revealed that Business Educators require productivity competency to a high extent for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 3 reveal the independent t-test analysis of the difference in mean responses of state and federal universities business educators on marketing productivity competency is required for teaching digital marketing in South-south Nigeria. Since the p-value is greater than the alpha level, the null hypothesis of the mean responses of state and federal university business educators do not differ significantly on the extent to which productivity competency is required for teaching digital

marketing in South-south Nigeria.” Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. The research findings and hypotheses align with the observations made by Sharma & Sharma (2014), who note that enhancing the productivity of business educators has emerged as a primary objective in numerous universities. This focus on increased employee productivity is driven by the numerous advantages it offers to both organizations and their staff. Notably, heightened productivity contributes to positive economic growth, enhanced profitability, and improved social progress. Additionally, Marchington and Wilkinson (2016) have similarly highlighted that the improper selection of business educators, stemming from flawed processes, can have severe repercussions on the outcomes of teaching and learning. Consequently, it is imperative to avoid such missteps, given their substantial potential negative impact on the quality of graduates as the end product.

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation on the extent to which marketing research competency is required by Business Educators for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria. The total mean of items were above the criterion mean of 2.50 which revealed that Business Educators require marketing research competency to a high extent for teaching digital marketing in federal and state universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 4 reveal the independent t-test analysis of the difference in mean responses of state and federal universities business educators on marketing research competencies required for teaching digital marketing in South-South Nigeria. Since the p-value is greater than the alpha level, the null hypothesis of the mean responses of state and federal university business educators does not differ significantly on the extent to which marketing research competencies are required for teaching digital marketing in South-South Nigeria.” Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is upheld. Though the research questions align with Trimmer's (2012) report, which concurs that proficiency in research is a vital requirement for conducting online research in the academic field, particularly in the realm of marketing. These essential skills can be acquired or refined through formal education, participation in seminars, and similar educational endeavors. Moreover, practical experience in research plays a significant role in augmenting research capabilities and outcomes, representing the next stage of advancement after improved educational preparation. While engaged in research, it is not uncommon to encounter unforeseen challenges and obstacles along the way.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscored the critical importance of a diverse set of competencies for business educators tasked with teaching of digital marketing in state and federal universities in South-South, Nigeria. To effectively prepare students for the dynamic and competitive world of digital marketing, business educators must possess digital marketing competencies in marketing productivity competency and marketing research competency.

The following recommendations were made based on the research objectives:

1. University administration, in conjunction with experienced project managers, should develop and oversee the implementation a project management training program tailored to digital marketing projects.

2. Curriculum development committees and academic departments should work together to integrate research methodologies and tools specific to digital marketing into the curriculum into the digital marketing course materials.

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